

The Australian Virtual Hub at the January 2026 ESIP Meeting

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Introduction

The January 2026 ESIP meeting was a fully virtual meeting held from 20-23 January 2026, and the same group who organised the Australian ESIP July 2025 Hub meeting decided to set up another Australian Hub for this ESIP meeting. The difference was that the January 2026 Hub was fully virtual (see Figure 1 for a screenshot of one of our Hub sessions), whereas the July 2025 Hub was held in-person in Canberra.

Figure 1: One of our Hub sessions

Set-up and logistics

While we originally considered in-person hubs in different cities across Australia, the timing of the ESIP meeting, during the late Australian summer holidays, meant we had few attendees - we ended up with 7 participants - and little time for planning, so we decided to organise a fully virtual hub instead. As for the previous Hub meeting [1, 2], all attendees had to register as virtual attendees for the main ESIP meeting.

Our Australian January 2026 ESIP hub spanned two time zones: Australian Eastern Daylight Saving Time (AEDT) for our Melbourne, Canberra, and Merimbula-based participants, and Australian Western Standard Time (AWST) for our Perth-based participants. US ESIP sessions were run between 11am and 5:30pm EST (4pm - 8:30pm UTC / 3:00am to 9:30am AEDT / 00:00 - 6:30am AWST) each day. Participants in the AEDT time zone were able to join the last daily session of the main ESIP meeting live, whereas this was not possible for participants in the AWST time zone.

To make sure everyone could participate in our Hub sessions, we negotiated 3 session times throughout the day that worked across both AEDT and AWST (11:30am-1pm AEDT / 8:30am-10am AWST, 1:30pm-3pm AEDT / 10:30am-12pm AWST and 3:30pm-5pm AEDT / 12:30pm-2pm AWST).

Prior to the Hub meeting, a spreadsheet with all ESIP sessions was shared (see Figure 2), and Hub participants were asked to nominate sessions they were interested in. The 7 sessions with at least 3 interested participants were slotted into one of the agreed session times, and calendar invitations were sent for those sessions, including the title of the respective session. In addition, on day 3, we scheduled one session for people to report on additional sessions they had watched, and one general feedback session.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
11								
12	Day 1 - Tuesday, January 20							
13	11:00 US Tuesday	3:00 AM AEST Wednesday	12:00 AM Wednesday	Opening Plenary: Owen Nevin (Western Australian Biodiversity Science Institute): "Shared Environmental Analytics Facility – Trusted Environmental Data and Information Supply Chains in Practice."				
14								
15	Interested:							
16	Zoom: ESIP staff will add streaming info							
17	Australian ESIP Hub Meeting time							
18	Friday, 11:30am AEDT / 8:30am AWST							
19	13:30 US ET Tuesday	5:30 AM Wednesday	2:30 AM Wednesday	Complex Citation Object Generator https://2026januaryesipmeeting.sched.com/e	Toward a Standard Chunk Manifest for https://2026januaryesipmeeting.sched.co	Enhancing Data Sharing Through https://2026januaryesipmeeting.sched.co	Teaching Machine Learning Techniques Using https://2026januaryesipmeeting.sched.com/ev	CivicScapes: Bridging Data with Civic Engagement in the https://2026januaryesipmeeting.sched.com/event/2c4u6/
20								
21	Interested:							
22	Zoom: ESIP staff will add streaming info							
23	Australian ESIP Hub Meeting time							
24	16:00 US ET Tuesday	8:00 AM Wednesday	5:00 AM Wednesday	The Future of ACDD: Charting the Course https://2026januaryesipmeeting.sched.com/e	The Air Quality Cluster: Where should it https://2026januaryesipmeeting.sched.co	Wed, 11:30 AEDT / 8:30 AWST Assess Your Data Repository's Resilience https://2026januaryesipmeeting.sched.co	From Data to Impact: Co-developing Earth https://2026januaryesipmeeting.sched.com/ev	Bridging the Tyranny of Time Zones to Enabling Effective https://2026januaryesipmeeting.sched.com/event/2c0v7/
25								
26	Interested:							
27	Zoom: ESIP staff will add streaming info							
28	Australian ESIP Hub Meeting time							
29	Wednesday, 1:30pm AEDT / 10:30 AWST							
30	Thursday, 11:30 AEDT / 8:30 AWST							
31	Wednesday, 3:30pm AEDT / 12:30 AWST							
32	Day 2 - Wednesday January 21							
33	11:00 US ET Wednesday	3:00 AM AEST Thursday	12:00 AM Thursday	Bridging Domain and Discipline Divides: https://2026januaryesipmeeting.sched.com/e	Bridging the Cloud Divide - Part 1 https://2026januaryesipmeeting.sched.co	How FAIR can you be? SWOT analysis of https://2026januaryesipmeeting.sched.co	Geophysical AI for Hazard Risk & Compliance https://2026januaryesipmeeting.sched.com/ev	Trusted Data Before, During, and After Disasters: The https://2026januaryesipmeeting.sched.com/event/2c0z7/
34								
35	Interested:							
36	Zoom: ESIP staff will add streaming info							
37	Australian ESIP Hub Meeting time							
38	Thursday, 2pm AEDT / 11am AWST							
39	Thursday, 4pm AEDT / 1:30pm AWST							
40	13:30 US ET Wednesday	5:30 AM Thursday	2:30 AM Thursday	Enabling Standards Compliance https://2026januaryesipmeeting.sched.com/e/vent/2c0x8/enabling-standards-compliance	Bridging the Cloud Divide - Part 2 https://2026januaryesipmeeting.sched.co/m/event/2c0x8/bridging-the-cloud-divide-part-2	Blowing in the wind: Workflow resilience https://2026januaryesipmeeting.sched.com/ev	Part 2 - Geophysical AI for Hazard Risk & https://2026januaryesipmeeting.sched.com/ev/ent/2c0v7/geophysical-ai-for-hazard-risk-compliance-mapping-part-2	Supporting the Earth Scientist Community - Spinning up a https://2026januaryesipmeeting.sched.com/event/2c0x8/supporting-the-earth-scientist-community-spinning-up-a-new-cluster
41								
42	Interested:							
43	Zoom: ESIP staff will add streaming info							
44	Not recorded							
45	Same recording as Part 1							
46	Not recorded							
47	Australian ESIP Hub Meeting time							

Figure 2: Spreadsheet shared with participants prior to Hub meeting

ESIP staff used our spreadsheet to provide links to the unedited recordings immediately after a session had finished and the recording had been minimally processed. We then accessed these recordings in the Hub meetings; in addition, participants could watch sessions that fewer than three participants were interested in at their own convenience.

What worked

Access to the recordings went well, with no technical hitches. Since we had access to all recordings, we were able to watch multiple sessions scheduled for the same time slot, which was actually better than attending live and having to pick at most one session per time slot.

Several people commented that pre-arranging viewing sessions meant they committed to carving out time to watch and discuss the session recordings. This helped make the Hub meeting feel more like an actual event. One person commented that they booked a physical meeting room for attendees from their organisation for these sessions, which increased this effect. In addition, having session times blocked out in participants' calendars meant that other people refrained from scheduling additional meetings unless absolutely necessary.

Despite the small number of participants (7), the virtual Hub worked quite well. Getting consensus on the sessions most people wanted to attend led to participants joining their selected sessions and to very engaged, enthusiastic discussions. Some people already started discussions in the chat throughout the sessions, while others seemed to prefer verbal discussion at selected times. One person commented that they found having a local expert who could lead discussions and provide background and additional information very valuable. One session worked through the interactive component of the recorded session instead of just watching the recording, which seemed to work very well and created insights that were fed back to the original session via the collaborative notes document.

Given that our Australian Hub sessions were the same length, listening to the full US recording left no time for our own discussions. For those sessions that provided really good notes, we could use these to review the key points of discussion, hold our own discussions and add our key points back to the session notes.

The Research Showcase was a virtual gallery of posters, recorded demos, and tutorials from ESIP Meeting attendees. As you were able to view all contributions at any time during the meeting and leave questions or comments for the contributors in Qiqochat, members of the Australian Hub could view contributions and comment on their own time. However, because the live session was scheduled for 4:00pm US ET (8:00pm AEDT), only East Coast Australians could join and interact directly with the presenters. As most hybrid conferences/meetings do not provide opportunities for virtual participants to interact with presenters, or even simply view posters, demos, etc, this was seen as a bonus.

What could be improved or trialled

Timing of the Meeting

We encountered several main challenges around the timing of the meeting. Firstly, the meeting was held in late January, at the end of the Australian Christmas and summer holiday break, which significantly reduced the number of potential participants.

Secondly, many Australians commence their Summer leave in mid-December, and because information about the ESIP January meeting schedule only became available in late December, organising the Australian Hub was quite difficult, as it was hard to interest people in the event when we did not have a program, particularly if they had never participated in an ESIP meeting.

Thirdly, whilst the three scheduled Hub sessions per day were manageable for most participants, and unscheduled time in the mornings (AEDT) / afternoons (AWST) meant that participants had time for their normal work, the different time zones made it difficult for us to join sessions live as a Hub. The 8:00-9:30am AEDT time slot was the only feasible option for participants in AEDT time zones, but it was hard for those in other Australian time zones and impossible for those in AWST, so we did not include it in our agenda.

Fourthly, difficulties arose for Hub attendees who co-facilitated or presented in live sessions. One participant was involved in several live sessions, with two held at 3:00am and 5:30am AEDT. Attending the subsequent 3 Hub sessions, which ended at 5:00pm AEDT, made for a very long, exhausting day. We would like to explore if we can make the Hub less of a satellite and more of an equal event by running 1-2 sessions live in the Hub (open to all ESIP meeting participants, but at a time convenient to the Hub) and providing a recording for the rest of the ESIP meeting to view at their own convenience.

Planning

For future Hubs, we aim to promote the Hub idea widely and early (about 2 months before the event) so we can explain to potential participants how the Hub will work, the dates for the Hub meeting, the expected number of sessions and their time slots per day, etc. We would also ask if any potential participants are willing to help us organise the Hub.

Once the ESIP meeting program is published, we will send out a second email to recruit additional participants and ask participants to nominate the sessions they are interested in. For the January 2026 meeting, we used a spreadsheet showing all ESIP sessions and asked participants to add their names to sessions they were interested in. The ESIP staff then added links to the recordings to this spreadsheet. This worked well with a small number of people, but we may need to adopt a different approach if the number increases significantly.

Local Content

For a larger number of participants, particularly if we run multiple Hubs, we would like to explore adding local content to our Australian Hub meetings to increase the feeling of the Hub as a cohesive event. This could include:

- Local poster and/or networking sessions, possibly even shared or held jointly with the main meeting. For example, a 2-min poster madness session with participants presenting on topics they are interested in or currently working on, followed by a networking session where they can talk with one another about these topics.
- Local presentations where some participants present in more depth about their work.

Increased Interaction with the ESIP Meeting

While it was possible to provide feedback, comments, and further input to session organisers by editing the collaborative session notes, this was a one-way street rather than a feedback loop, as there were no responses to our edits, and we did not know whether the session organisers ever read them. We think there are a few things that could increase the interaction between the Hub and the main meeting:

Raising awareness: During the July 2025 Hub meeting, the “Australian Hub” was mentioned a few times in the live sessions (both by us and by session organisers), we used a photo of the Hub as our Zoom avatar for sessions we joined live, and we also posted about the Hub on the dedicated ESIP July meeting Slack channel about the Hub. All of these small activities seemed to help raise awareness. During the January 2026 Hub meeting, we were less able to join sessions live due to time differences; there did not seem to be a dedicated Slack channel for the meeting, and the main Hub seemed less aware of us.

For future Hub meetings, we suggest a few “promotional” activities to raise awareness of the Hub in the main ESIP meeting. For example, we could create a slide or a 1-2-minute video about the who, what, and why of the Hub, which could then be presented or played during the opening session and published on the ESIP Slack. One point we could make is that we add our input, comments, and feedback to the collaborative session notes, and we would really appreciate it if the session organisers responded to us.

Exploring asynchronous interaction: As noted above, we tried to interact asynchronously with the main ESIP meeting by providing comments and feedback through the collaborative session notes and posting on the ESIP Slack. However, there may be better ways to interact, both within the current ESIP communication channels. For example, it was unclear to us how many meeting participants actually use Slack, or whether we should have used any other communication channels (e.g., Qiqochat). It would be useful for us to gain a better understanding of how communication works within ESIP and where we should focus our efforts. It would also be helpful to us if ESIP could encourage session organisers to provide more detailed session descriptions, especially for Plenary sessions, which for both the January 2026 and July 2025 Meetings were very sparse - some only listed the speakers. It is also very helpful

if the session notes include links to the slides presented and provide more comprehensive notes that outline the main discussions and any key actions or decisions taken.

Joint activities: We are keen to explore activities, especially asynchronous activities, that demonstrate the value of engaging participants across the main meeting and the Hub. For example, we could organise a multi-part session with a specific topic, with a sequence of activities in the ESIP meeting and the Hub, perhaps similar to a 24-hour book sprint. One such topic could be the generation of a “wishlist” from participants, describing an ideal virtual participation at a hybrid event, such as the ESIP meeting.

Concluding Remarks

Both the in-person Hub at the ESIP July 2025 meeting and the virtual Hub at the ESIP January 2026 meeting successfully brought together Australian participants, created engaging discussions, and fostered connections. We would like to continue our exploration of the Hub model and hope that, in the future, we will be able to trial connecting a couple of Hubs in similar time zones together for joint activities. We are also interested in mixing virtual and in-person sessions in our Hubs, e.g., running a virtual Hub on two days and an in-person Hub focused on networking activities on a third day. We are also very interested in connecting with others in the ESIP community who have further suggestions for us or are interested in organising their own Hubs.

Acknowledgements

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References

[1] Wyborn, L., Klump, J., & Kethers, S. (2025). Report on the ESIP July 2025 Hub meeting, Canberra 23-25 July 2025. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17015198>

[2] Gentes, Zoe (2025): Hub-and-Spoke Remote Meetings Could Be a New Model for Collaboration. ESIP Blog post, 20 August 2025: <https://www.esipfed.org/hub-and-spoke-remote-meetings-could-be-a-new-model-for-collaboration/>